

ON THE BALU NUMBERS

Maohua Le

Abstract . In this paper we prove that there are only finitely many Balu numbers .

Key words . Smarandache factor partition , number of divisors , Balu number , finiteness .

1.Introductio

For any positive integer n , let $d(n)$ and $f(n)$ be the number of distinct divisors and the Smarandache factor partitions of n respectively. If n is the least positive integer satisfying

$$(1) \quad d(n)=f(n)=r$$

for some fixed positive integers r , then n is called a Balu number. For example , $n=1,16,36$ are Balu numbers. In [4], Murthy proposed the following conjecture.

Conjecture. There are finitely many Balu numbers.

In this paper we completely solve the mentioned question. We prove the following result .

Theorem. There are finitely many Balu numbers .

2.Preliminaries

For any positive integer n with $n>1$, let

$$(2) \quad n = p_1^{a_1} p_2^{a_2} \dots p_k^{a_k}$$

be the factorization of n .

Lemma 1 ([1, Theorem 273]) . $d(n)=(a_1+1)(a_2+1)\dots(a_k+1)$.

Lemma 2. Let a, p be positive integers with $p > 1$, and let

$$(3) \quad b = \left[\frac{1}{2} \sqrt{1+8a} - \frac{1}{2} \right].$$

Then p^a can be written as a product of b distinct positive integers

$$(4) \quad p^a = p \cdot p^2 \cdots p^{b-1} p^{a-b(b-1)/2}.$$

Proof. We see from (3) that $a \geq 1+2+\dots+(b-1)+b$. Thus, the lemma is true.

Lemma 3. For any positive integer m , let $Y(m)$ be the m -th Bell number. Then we have

$$(5) \quad f(n) \geq Y(c),$$

where

$$(6) \quad c = b_1 + b_2 + \dots + b_k$$

and

$$(7) \quad b_i = \left[\frac{1}{2} \sqrt{1+8a_i} - \frac{1}{2} \right], \quad i=1,2,\dots,k.$$

Proof. Since p_1, p_2, \dots, p_k are distinct primes in the factorization (2) of n , by Lemma 2, we see from (6) and (7) that n can be written as a product of c distinct positive integers

$$(8) \quad n = \prod_{i=1}^k \left[p_i^{a_i - b_i(b_i-1)/2} \prod_{j=1}^{b_i-1} p_i^j \right].$$

Therefore, by (6) and (8), we get

$$(9) \quad f(n) \geq F(1\#c),$$

where $F(1\#c)$ is the number of Smarandache factor partitions of a product of c distinct primes. Further, by [2, Theorem], we have

$$(10) \quad F(1\#c) = Y(c).$$

Thus, by (9) and (10), we obtain (5). The lemma is

proved .

Lemma 4 ([3]) . $\log Y(m) \sim m \log m$.

3.Proof of Theorem

We now suppose that there exist infinitely many Balu numbers . Let n be a Balu number , and let (2) be the factorization of n . Further , let

$$(11) \quad a = a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_k .$$

Clear , if n is enough large , then a tends to infinite . Moreover , since

$$(12) \quad b_i \geq \sqrt{a} \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, k ,$$

by (7) , we see from (6) that c tends to infinite too . Therefore , by Lemmas 1 , 3 and 4 , we get from (1), (2), (6) and (12) that

$$(13) \quad 1 = \frac{\log d(n)}{\log f(n)} \leq \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k \log(a_i+1)}{\left(\sum_{i=1}^k \sqrt{a_i} \right) \left(\log \sum_{i=1}^k \sqrt{a_i} \right)}$$

$$\leq \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k \log(a_i+1)}{k \sum_{i=1}^k \sqrt{a_i}} < 1 ,$$

a contradiction . Thus , there are finitely many Balu numbers . The theorem is proved .

References

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Department of Mathematics
Zhanjiang Normal College
Zhanjiang, Guangdong
P.R. CHINA